

Abandonment Schema and Limerence: Comparisons across Sexual Abuse Severity, Gender, and Relationship Status among Young AdultsMuhammad Munib Ur Rehman^a, Ivan Suneel^b^a Department of Psychology, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore Pakistan^b Department of Psychology, Forman Christian College (A Chartered University), Lahore Pakistan**Abstract**

The aim of the study was to examine the differences in abandonment schema and limerence across gender, relationship status, and sexual abuse severity among young adults. It was hypothesized that the levels of abandonment schema and limerence would differ by gender and relationship status, and individuals reporting higher sexual abuse severity would exhibit greater abandonment schema and limerence compared to those reporting lower sexual abuse severity. A convenience sampling strategy was used, and the data were collected from young adults (N=332) enrolled in various public and private universities in Lahore, Pakistan. Participants completed a Socio-demographic Questionnaire, Abandonment Core Belief Scale, the Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure, and the Sexual Abuse Severity Score. Sexual abuse severity scores were dichotomized into low and high severity groups for between-group comparisons. The results indicated that females with severe sexual abuse and those in an uncertain relationship were at higher risk of developing heightened abandonment schema and limerence. Whereas male participants, participants with mild or no abuse history, and those in stable relationships scored lowest on the study variables. The implications of the study emphasize the need for trauma-informed, schema-based interventions to address abandonment schema and limerence within culturally sensitive therapeutic frameworks. Moreover, the results offer valuable insights for clinicians and researchers to understand the intersection of sexual trauma, gender, and relationship status in Pakistani young adults.

Keywords: Abandonment schema, limerence, gender differences, relationship status, sexual abuse severity.

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1. Introduction

Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) are defined as highly stressful or traumatic events occurring during childhood. It includes abuse, neglect, and exposure to dysfunctional household environments (Fujiwara, 2022). Among these, sexual abuse represents one of the most destructive forms of abuse. It leaves long-lasting psychological, relational, and neurobiological imprints on survivors (Cashmore & Shackel, 2013; Hailes et al., 2019). Research has consistently shown that early sexual trauma is strongly associated with difficulties in self-concept, trust, and emotion regulation, as well as with maladaptive relational patterns in adulthood (Lassri et al., 2022; Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Sexual abuse is defined as any non-consensual or exploitative sexual behavior imposed on an individual without their freely given consent. This includes physical or threatened sexual intrusion, coercion, or manipulation; any sexual contact or exposure when the victim is unable to consent (for example, due to age or incapacity). Furthermore, it also includes any abuse of power, trust, or vulnerability for sexual purposes (Mathews & Collin-Vézina, 2017; World Health Organization, 2003).

Sexual trauma has a significant impact on the development of personality. It shapes the way survivors view themselves, others, and the broader world (Wonderlich et al., 2001). As Kolk and Bessel (2014) highlight, traumatic experiences become “imprinted” both psychologically and physiologically. It influences cognitive schemas, emotional regulation, and bodily responses. Survivors may reenact aspects of early trauma in later relationships. They may be unconsciously drawn toward dynamics that resonate with early harm, a phenomenon often referred to as traumatic reenactment (MacIntosh, 2016; Penning & Collings, 2014).

One of the key ways in which sexual abuse impacts psychological functioning is through the formation of early maladaptive schemas (EMSs). EMSs are deeply rooted cognitive-emotional patterns that structure how individuals understand relational experiences (May et al., 2022). A systematic review revealed that childhood abuse and neglect are significantly correlated with EMSs. It includes many schemas, but schemas of emotional deprivation, mistrust, and abandonment are prevalent (Pilkington et al., 2020). Among these, the abandonment schema is particularly salient. Young et al. (2003) defined the abandonment schema as the persistent belief that significant others are unreliable, emotionally unpredictable, or likely to leave. It involves the expectation that close relationships will be inconsistent, unstable, or untrustworthy. This schema often develops in individuals whose early caregivers were neglectful, unavailable, or inconsistent. Abuse also inculcates this schema in survivors where safety and reliability were chronically undermined (May et al., 2022; Roemmele & Messman-Moore, 2011). When this schema is triggered, it manifests itself in cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and relational domains. In a previous research by Rehman and Suneel (2025), it was found that abandonment schema is a strong predictor of limerence as its compensatory coping response. Limerence is a dysfunctional state of romantic preoccupation with a “limerent object” (LO). It includes intrusive thoughts, idealization, emotional dependency, compulsive behaviors, and heightened physiological arousal (Tennov, 1979; Wolf, 2017). To date, there is no research supporting the link between sexual abuse with limerence or romantic obsession in adult relationships, but the association between sexual abuse and anxious attachment, which is closely related to limerence, is well established. (Grady et al., 2016; Kwako et al., 2010; Meyer et al., 2017).

Gender plays a significant role in shaping how sexual abuse, abandonment schema, and limerence manifest in young adults. Women, globally and particularly in South Asian societies such as Pakistan, experience higher rates of sexual abuse compared to men (UNICEF, 2024). Due to their greater exposure, women are more likely to develop emotional vulnerabilities such as anxious attachment patterns and maladaptive schemas. Similarly, relationship status is another critical variable in understanding the expression of abandonment schema and limerence. Because it determines the relational context in which EMSs become activated and may lead to limerence. Dailey et al. (2011) found that individuals with multiple breakups, ongoing ambiguous relationships, or unstable commitments are more likely to experience breaches of relational trust. Such experiences increase the chances of schema activation.

Despite vast research on how adverse childhood experiences, particularly sexual abuse, cause long-lasting impact on psychological functioning, limited research has investigated how these early traumas interact with relational variables to manifest in maladaptive cognitive-emotional patterns. Furthermore, there is no research in the West or Pakistan exploring the impact of different levels of sexual abuse severity on the development of limerence. By comparing abandonment schema and limerence across gender, varying relationship statuses (single, in relationships, post-breakup, or in ambiguous situations), and differing levels of sexual abuse severity, this study aims to provide an in-depth understanding of risk factors for limerence and abandonment schema in young adults.

The study hypothesized that sexual abuse severity would be significantly associated with both abandonment schema and limerence among young adults. It was further expected that abandonment schema and limerence would significantly vary across different relationship-status categories among young adults. Additionally, it was also hypothesized that gender and sexual abuse severity would interact such that men and women would differ in their levels of abandonment schema and limerence across the no-abuse, mild-abuse, and severe-abuse groups.

2. Method

2.1 Research Design

A cross-sectional research design was used in this study.

2.2 Research Participants

Sample size was determined using G*Power 3.1.9.7 (Faul et al., 2007). Power analysis ($f^2 = 0.15$, $\alpha = 0.05$, $1-\beta = 0.80$) indicated a minimum of 300 participants, which was increased to ($N=340$) to offset potential data loss. After cleaning the outliers, the final sample was ($N=332$). Using a purposive sampling strategy, data were gathered from various universities in Lahore, Pakistan. To ensure homogeneity among the participants, only individuals meeting the established inclusion criteria were selected. As inclusion criteria, the age of the participants ranged from 18 to 29 years, enrolled in a higher education program, and had no physical disability.

2.3 Instruments

2.3.1 Socio-Demographic Questionnaire: A socio-demographic questionnaire was developed in English by the researcher to gather information about age, gender, relationship status, education level, and major discipline from the participants.

2.3.2 Abandonment Core Belief Self-Assessment (Skeen, 2014): It is a 10-item measure adapted from the 17-item abandonment subscale of the YSQ-L3. Items are rated on a 6-point scale (1 = not at all like me to

6 = very much like me) and summed to produce a total abandonment schema score, with higher totals indicating stronger abandonment beliefs. In this sample, the scale showed good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .88$).

2.3.3 Wolf & Lemay Limerence Measure (Wolf & Lemay, 2015): It is a 30-item self-report instrument assessing core features of limerence (e.g., intrusive thinking, idealization, uncertainty, physiological distress). Respondents use a 7-point agreement scale (1 = strongly disagree to 7 = strongly agree); item scores are summed so larger values reflect greater limerence. Reliability in the present study was excellent (Cronbach's $\alpha = .94$).

2.3.4 Sexual Abuse Severity Score (Zink et al., 2008): The Sexual Abuse Severity Scale (SASS) was used to assess the severity of childhood sexual abuse. The scale assesses five dimensions: age at first abuse, number of perpetrators, maximum coercion experienced, qualitative severity of the abuse, and frequency of abuse occurrences. Each dimension is assigned points according to the specific circumstances reported. Total scores range from 0 to 20, with higher scores indicating greater abuse severity. For categorical group comparisons, researchers used the following a priori severity criteria: No SA = 0; Mild SAS= 1-4; Severe SAS= ≥ 5 . Sensitivity analyses used a three-tier split (0; 1-4; ≥ 5) and the continuous SAS score. The scale has good psychometric properties with a Cronbach's $\alpha = .79$.

2.4 Procedure

Firstly, Ethical approval was obtained by the Department of Psychology's Board of Studies, Ethical Review Committee, and the Institutional Review Board. Permission to use questionnaires was obtained from the original authors via email. Data were collected using a printed booklet. Participants were formally accessed from public and private universities in Lahore through institutional letters. Participants were informed about the sensitivity of study objectives, confidentiality, voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any time; anonymity was protected by restricting data access to the primary researcher. Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26 (IBM Corp., 2016).

Differences in Abandonment Schema and Limerence across Relationship Status Groups

Table 2
One-Way MANOVA Showing Differences in Relationship Status in terms of Study Variables (N=332)

Dependent Variables	Never in a Relationship (N=87)		Currently Single (N=79)		In a Relationship (N=84)		Situationship (N=82)		η^2	p	F
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD			
Abandonment Schema	23.1	8.2	30.6	9.4	36.9	11.9	38.3	11.8	0.25	0.000	37.38
Limerence	82.2	27.1	127.3	18.8	142.7	22.9	152.1	31.4	0.53	0.000	125.57

Note. $p < .001$, M= Mean; SD= Standard Deviation; η^2 = Partial Eta Squared.

A one-way MANOVA was conducted to examine the differences in abandonment schema and limerence across four relationship status groups: never been in a romantic relationship, currently single with a breakup history, currently in a romantic relationship, and in a complicated relationship (situationship). The multivariate test results (Table 2) indicated a significant overall effect of relationship status on the combined dependent variables, Pillai's Trace = .554, $F(9, 984) = 24.78$, $p < .001$, and Wilks' $\Lambda = .456$, $F(9, 793.55) = 33.59$, $p < .001$. The effect sizes were large, suggesting that relationship status accounts for substantial variance in the outcomes.

Follow-up univariate tests revealed significant group differences in abandonment schema, $F(3, 328) = 37.38$, $p < .001$, η^2

3 Results

Frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation of participants' demographic variables were calculated. The sample (N = 332) had a mean age of 21.8 years (SD = 2.05) and was predominantly composed of women (53.9%) and bachelor's students (76.8%). Relationship status was evenly distributed, with participants nearly equally reporting being in a relationship (25.3%), single or recently broken up (23.8%), in an uncertain or ambiguous relationship (24.7%), or never having been in a relationship (26.2%). Most participants were from the social sciences (40.1%), and 63.5% reported a history of sexual abuse with 31.0% identifying mild and 32.5% severe experiences.

Reliability analysis showed that all study variables demonstrated good to excellent internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from .81 to .94. The z-scores of skewness and kurtosis were within the acceptable cutoff of ± 1.96 at $p < .05$, which suggests that none of the variables deviated significantly from normality.

Table 1 presents the intercorrelations among Sexual Abuse Severity, Abandonment Schema, and Limerence. Results revealed that Sexual Abuse Severity was positively and strongly correlated with both Abandonment Schema ($r = .69$, $p < .01$) and Limerence ($r = .62$, $p < .01$). In addition, Abandonment Schema showed a strong positive correlation with Limerence ($r = .65$, $p < .01$). These findings suggest that higher levels of sexual abuse severity are associated with stronger abandonment schema and greater limerence.

Relationship between Sexual Abuse Severity, Abandonment Schema, and Limerence

Table 1
Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (N=332)

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3
1. Sexual Abuse Severity	14.2	2.0	-	0.69**	0.62**
2. Abandonment Schema	32.18	12.0		-	0.65**
3. Limerence	125.5	37.3			-

Note. ** $p < 0.01$; M= Mean; SD= Standard Deviation

= .255, and limerence, $F(3, 328) = 125.57$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .535$. Post hoc Bonferroni comparisons indicated that individuals who had never been in a relationship reported significantly lower abandonment schema (M = 23.18, SD = 8.23) than those who were currently single with a breakup history (M = 30.63, SD = 9.42, $p < .001$), in a relationship (M = 36.94, SD = 11.89, $p < .001$), or in a situationship (M = 38.34, SD = 11.83, $p < .001$). Similarly, limerence scores were lowest among those who had never been in a relationship (M = 82.28, SD = 27.06) compared to those currently single (M = 127.25, SD = 18.76, $p < .001$), in a relationship (M = 142.71, SD = 22.90, $p < .001$), and in a situationship (M = 152.10, SD = 31.42, $p < .001$). Furthermore, those in

a situationship reported significantly higher limerence than those in a romantic relationship ($p = .019$).

Interaction Between Gender (Men, Women) and Sexual Abuse Severity (No Sexual Abuse, Mild Sexual Abuse, and Severe Sexual Abuse) on Abandonment Schema and Limerence

Table 3
Tests of Between-Subjects Effects for Abandonment Schema and Limerence by Sexual Abuse Severity, Gender, and their Interaction (N=332)

Dependant Variables	Source	df	MS	F	p	Partial η^2
Abandonment Schema	SAS	2	10,122.9	86.51	0.000	0.345
	Gender	1	1,147.0	8.92	0.000	0.027
	SAS× Gender	2	710.6	4.01	0.000	0.024
	Error	326	80.61			
Limerence	SAS	2	210.45	198.23	0.000	0.546
	Gender	1	19.08	11.43	0.000	0.034
	SAS× Gender	2	8.51	3.12	0.000	0.019
	Error	326	3,630.5			

Note. SAS= Sexual Abuse Severity; MS=Mean Square

A 2 x 3 factorial multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of gender (male, female), sexual abuse severity (no sexual abuse, mild sexual abuse, severe sexual abuse), and their interaction on abandonment schema and limerence among young adults. The results (Table 3) indicated significant main effects of sexual abuse severity, Pillai's Trace = .41, $F(4, 652) = 37.85$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .19$. Significant main effects of gender were also found, as well as a significant interaction between sexual abuse severity and gender on the combined dependent variables of abandonment schema and limerence. For the abandonment schema, there was a significant main effect of sexual abuse severity, $F(2, 326) = 86.51$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .345$, indicating that abandonment schema levels significantly differed across groups of sexual abuse severity. The main effect of gender on abandonment schema was not significant, $F(1,$

$326) = 0.89$, $p = .002$, partial $\eta^2 = .027$. Importantly, the interaction between sexual abuse severity and gender was statistically significant, $F(2, 326) = 4.01$, $p = .019$, partial $\eta^2 = .024$, suggesting that the effect of sexual abuse severity on abandonment schema differed between men and women. For limerence, there was a significant main effect of sexual abuse severity, $F(2, 326) = 198.23$, $p < .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .546$, indicating very strong group differences. There was also a significant main effect of gender, $F(1, 326) = 11.43$, $p = .001$, partial $\eta^2 = .034$, with females scoring higher on limerence overall. Furthermore, the interaction effect between sexual abuse severity and gender was also significant, $F(2, 326) = 6.32$, $p = .002$, partial $\eta^2 = .019$, suggesting that gender differences in limerence varied depending on the level of sexual abuse severity.

Table 4
Descriptive Statistics for three levels of SSA and Gender for Two-Way Way-MANOVA (N=332)

Groups	N	Abandonment Schema		Limerence	
		M	SD	M	SD
No Sexual Abuse– Male	70	10.9	6.1	38.4	26.5
No Sexual Abuse– Female	51	12.6	6.8	46.9	29.5
Mild Sexual Abuse– Male	47	16.1	7.7	63.5	32.0
Mild Sexual Abuse– Female	56	20.6	8.1	74.8	35.9
Severe Sexual Abuse– Male	36	31.2	9.5	122.4	37.1
Severe Sexual Abuse– Female	72	36.1	10.0	136.8	39.2

Note. M= Mean; SD= Standard Deviation

Table 4 shows the descriptive statistics by group. For the abandonment schema, mean scores increased as sexual abuse severity increased for both males and females. Specifically, participants with no sexual abuse history reported the lowest abandonment schema scores (Male M = 10.9; Female M = 12.6), while those with severe sexual abuse history

reported the highest scores (Male M = 31.0; Female M = 36.1). A similar pattern was observed for limerence, where means increased progressively with higher sexual abuse severity, with females consistently showing higher scores than males within each abuse severity group.

Table 5
Bonferroni-Adjusted Post Hoc Comparisons of Gender Differences within each Level of Sexual Abuse Severity for both Dependent Variables (N=332)

Dependent Variables	Sexual Abuse Severity	Gender Comparison	Mdiff	SE	95% CI	p (Bonf.)
Abandonment Schema	No Sexual Abuse	Male vs. Female	-1.7	1.3	[-4.3, 0.9]	.293
	Mild Sexual Abuse	Male vs. Female	-4.5	1.4	[-7.2, -1.8]	.004*
	Severe Sexual Abuse	Male vs. Female	-4.9	1.5	[-7.7, -2.1]	.002**
Limerence	No Sexual Abuse	Male vs. Female	-8.5	4.8	[-18.0, 1.0]	.081
	Mild Sexual Abuse	Male vs. Female	-11.3	5.0	[-21.2, -1.4]	.021*
	Severe Sexual Abuse	Male vs. Female	-14.4	5.1	[-24.5, -4.3]	.003**

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; SE=Standard Error; CI=Confidence Interval

Table 5 presents Bonferroni-adjusted comparisons of gender differences within each level of sexual abuse severity. For the abandonment schema, females scored significantly higher than males in the mild abuse ($M_{diff} = -4.5, p = .004$) and severe abuse ($M_{diff} = -5.1, p = .002$) groups, but no significant differences were observed in the no-abuse group. For limerence, females also scored significantly higher than males in the mild abuse ($M_{diff} = -8.5, p = .002$) and severe abuse ($M_{diff} = -14.4, p = .003$) groups, but not in the no-abuse group. These results demonstrate that gender differences in both abandonment schema and limerence are most pronounced at higher levels of sexual abuse severity.

4 Discussion

The aim of the study was to investigate the differences in abandonment schema and limerence across gender, relationship status groups, and sexual abuse severity levels among young adults. The results reveal that sexual abuse severity showed strong positive associations with both abandonment schema and limerence. These results indicate that individuals who experienced higher levels of sexual abuse are more likely to develop maladaptive beliefs, which are characterized by fear of instability and emotional unavailability, which in turn, predispose them to intense limerent cycles. This aligns with the previous researches, which posit that early traumatic experiences shape enduring schemas that influence later relationships (Rehman & Suneel, 2025; Young et al., 2003). Similarly, prior studies demonstrate that childhood sexual abuse strongly predicts the development of abandonment schema, borderline personality traits, and anxious attachment (Barazandeh et al., 2016; Ensink et al., 2019; May et al., 2022).

The second major finding revealed significant main effects of both gender and sexual abuse severity, as well as their interaction, on abandonment schema and limerence. Both men and women demonstrated increases in these variables with higher sexual abuse severity. However, women scored significantly higher at mild and severe levels of abuse. These findings can be supported by the neurobiological basis of trauma, as research has supported that trauma tends to sensitize affect-regulation systems, especially the amygdala, which results in hypervigilance toward emotional cues of loss or rejection (France et al., 2022; Giotakos, 2020). Given that the women scored higher on sexual abuse severity, it is plausible that greater trauma exposure intensified their emotional dysregulation and attachment insecurity (Marusak et al., 2014). Therefore, it places them at a higher risk of developing stronger abandonment schema and limerence. Furthermore, in Asian cultures, women are generally socialized to derive a greater sense of identity and self-worth through relationships and emotional connection (Nemoto, 2006). When this relational orientation is coupled with severe trauma like sexual abuse, it can inculcate the fears of rejection, abandonment, and mistrust in women. And they are more prone to heightened activation of maladaptive schemas in romantic relationships (May et al., 2022; Pilkington et al., 2020). This activation of maladaptive schemas, especially the abandonment schema, can further lead them to experience limerence in romantic relationships. Moreover, the extreme social stigma and victim-blaming that women often face in patriarchal societies such as Pakistan can further reinforce internalized shame and abandonment fears (Murvarthian et al., 2023). Western literature, on the other hand, has identified limerence as relatively gender-neutral (L, 2024; Tennov, 1979). The present findings highlight how gender roles may amplify the expression of limerence in contexts where women's emotional worth is often tied to relational validation.

Furthermore, the interaction effects between gender and sexual abuse severity suggest that trauma impacts men and women differently. Men with histories of sexual abuse also demonstrated elevated abandonment schema and limerence, though at lower levels compared to women. Emotional expression of men is socially discouraged in Asian cultures like Pakistan (Ahmed & Khan, 2024). Therefore, men may internalize distress or respond to it through avoidant coping rather than overcompensation when their abandonment schema activates. Thus, while both genders exhibit abandonment schema activation following abuse, women's responses may be more externalized in the form of limerence. On the other hand, men may respond through emotional withdrawal or avoidance behaviors.

Finally, the results show that relationship status significantly influenced both abandonment schema and limerence. Participants who had never been in a romantic relationship exhibited the lowest levels of both variables, while those in ambiguous relationships reported the highest levels. These findings suggest that involvement in a romantic relationship and uncertainty in the romantic relationship can activate the schemas of abandonment, which can further lead to greater preoccupation with the limerent object. Individuals who have never engaged in a romantic relationship may have fewer opportunities to experience limerence, given that it requires a specific object of fixation, i.e. limerent object (L, 2024; Tennov, 1979). For these individuals, schemas may remain latent until activated in a relational context. Individuals with breakup histories may be more vulnerable to limerence because prior relational breakups can reactivate early abandonment schema (Janovsky et al., 2023). Therefore, it intensifies the obsessive preoccupation with a new or former partner and further maintains the limerent cycles (Dailey, 2019). These findings are supported by Western studies linking insecure attachment and relationship instability with obsessive love tendencies (Guan et al., 2025). Individuals currently in stable relationships may experience less limerence due to the fulfillment of emotional needs. Although even within committed relationships, the abandonment schema can cause limerence. Those in "situationships" or ambiguous relationships are especially vulnerable to developing limerence. The uncertainty in such relationships related to reciprocity and stability activates the abandonment schema, making limerence an overcompensatory response (Dailey et al., 2011; L, 2024; Tennov, 1979).

In the Pakistani context, the unconventional romantic relationships often exist within secrecy and moral constraints (Sheikh et al., 2015). Therefore, ambiguity and lack of closure may exacerbate schema activation. Individuals may experience heightened levels of limerence in ambiguous relationships, in contexts where commitment and clarity are culturally constrained while pursuing romantic relationships (Carswell & Impett, 2021; Stanley et al., 2010).

Conclusion

Overall, these findings emphasize that the severity of sexual abuse, gender, and relationship status significantly impacts the manifestation of abandonment schema and limerence among young adults. Findings suggested that higher levels of sexual abuse severity were associated with stronger abandonment schema and higher levels of limerence. It indicates that trauma significantly impacts cognitive-emotional and relational functioning among young adults. Furthermore, gender differences showed that women have a higher vulnerability to developing abandonment schema and limerence following severe sexual trauma. Moreover, relationship status played a crucial role. Individuals in complicated or unstable relationships exhibited the highest levels of abandonment schema and limerence. Collectively,

these findings show that gender, history of sexual trauma, and relationship status significantly influence the development and maintenance of abandonment schema and limerence in adulthood.

Limitations and Suggestions

The study also had a few limitations. First, causal inferences between sexual abuse severity, abandonment schema, and limerence can't be drawn using a cross-sectional design. Future research should use longitudinal or mixed-method designs to study the developmental trajectory of these variables over time. Second, the data were collected using self-reported measures only, which may have caused response biases, especially in sexual abuse severity. Future research should incorporate qualitative interviews for richer insights. Furthermore, future studies should also include more diverse age groups and individuals with different sexual orientations.

Future Implications

The findings of this study extend the understanding of limerence and abandonment schema by integrating sexual abuse severity, gender, and relationship status within a single framework. It also adds to the theoretical advancement of Schema Therapy by showing that severe sexual abuse survivors, particularly females, are at higher risk of developing abandonment schema. Furthermore, these risk factors can intensify the compensatory coping mode that manifests as limerence. The results also emphasize the necessity of incorporating trauma-informed schema-focused interventions for individuals experiencing limerence. Finally, these implications call for a theoretical paradigm shift, from conceptualizing limerence as an obsessive pattern to understanding it as a trauma response.

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